

Supplementary material for the paper: Prediction of binaural speech intelligibility in noise and reverberation for normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners

Raphael Cueille^{1,2} and Mathieu Lavandier¹

¹*Univ. Lyon, ENTPE, Ecole Centrale de Lyon, CNRS, LTDS, UMR5513, Vaulx-en-Velin 69518, France*

²*CRNL, UMR CNRS 5292, Univ. Lyon 1, 50 av T Garnier, Lyon Cedex 07 69366, France*

Supplementary figure 1: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier *et al.* (2012). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*.

Supplementary figure 2: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier and Culling (2008). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*.

Supplementary figure 3: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their first experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*.

Supplementary figure 4: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their fourth experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*.

Supplementary figure 5: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Vicente et al. (2021). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the version of the proposed model that uses a room-independent ELL and an internal noise depending on the external sound spectrum, and for *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*. The predictions of *leclere2015* model are identical with stationary and modulated noise.

Supplementary figure 6: Scatter plots of measured and predicted SRTs for the HI listeners from Cueille et al. (2022), with the two internal noise calculations (broadband level vs. spectrum). Within each panel the Pearson correlation coefficient and the mean and largest absolute error between measured and predicted SRTs are specified in the upper left corner.

The solid lines mark identity between data and predictions.

Supplementary figure 7: Scatter plots of measured and predicted SRTs for the HI listeners from Vicente et al. (2021), with the two internal noise calculations (broadband level vs. spectrum). Within each panel the Pearson correlation coefficient and the mean and largest absolute error between measured and predicted SRTs are specified in the upper left corner.

The solid lines mark identity between data and predictions.